

A comprehensive investigation into the effect of vertical component of ground motion on response of sliding unanchored blocks

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to quantify the effect of the vertical component of ground motion on the seismic response of sliding rigid blocks, in terms of maximum and residual displacements. A multi-stripe analysis approach is employed to examine the response with and without the vertical component under various levels of ground motion intensity. First, a parametric study is conducted using a Coulomb friction model with a constant coefficient of friction that does not account for any dependence of the friction coefficient on velocity or pressure. It is shown that the effect of the vertical component on maximum and residual displacement is more pronounced for ground motions that can barely initiate sliding. Moreover, the influence of the vertical component on the residual sliding displacement is higher than that on the maximum displacement. Subsequently, to account for the friction coefficient dependence on pressure and sliding velocity, two interface cases (steel-steel, and concrete-concrete) are analyzed. It is found that even when a variable coefficient of friction is used, the overall trends observed for a constant coefficient of friction do not change.

1. Introduction

Earthquake induced damage is not limited to the structural elements of structures, but also includes non-structural components, such as furniture, ceilings, electrical systems, and architectural partitions. Non-structural components are responsible for a significant portion of the total damage associated with earthquakes [1,2]. Functional constraints often do not allow for anchoring of non-structural components and they are often free to rock, slide, jump or impact other components during earthquakes. The rocking response of objects has been extensively studied [3–16], for example. This study explores the sliding response of block-type objects.

To date, numerous studies on the response of sliding non-structural block-type objects have been carried out [17–28]. Among others, studies [18–20,22] investigated the sliding behavior of unanchored blocks subjected to horizontal earthquake excitations. Lopez Garcia and Soong [21] performed a fragility analysis of the sliding block under horizontal and vertical earthquakes. They found that neglecting the vertical excitation resulted in non-conservative estimates of maximum

sliding displacement. It is worth noting that this study assumed that the magnitude of the vertical component was proportional to that of the horizontal one. Arshad and Konstantinidis [28] examined the influence of the vertical floor excitation on the maximum sliding response of blocks in nuclear facilities. Moreover, Konstantinidis and Nikfar [24,26] studied the response of sliding blocks in based-isolated buildings, including the effect of the vertical earthquake component. More recently, Wang et al. [29] investigated the seismic responses of unanchored non-structural components in steel moment frames under horizontal and vertical earthquakes.

Cilsalar and Constantinou [30] studied the influence of the vertical component of the excitation on the response of structures isolated on concave sliding bearings – but this work is not directly applicable to sliding equipment, as bearings are designed to provide restoring force, while sliding equipment presents only friction.

The above-mentioned studies mainly focus on the *maximum* sliding response of the unanchored rigid block under earthquake excitations, because excessive sliding displacement can cause blocks to fall off shelves or collide with important objects [20,24]. However, the *residual*

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sliding displacement is often also important, even if there is no impact with adjacent objects. For example, residual displacements of rigid blocks after earthquakes can be used to estimate the intensity of ground motion [31,32], in the absence of recorded data. Furthermore, the residual displacement of pallets stored on steel racks in automated warehouses should be minimized so that the automatic systems used to move the pallets can function after an earthquake [33]. To the authors' knowledge, the effect of the vertical earthquake component on the residual sliding displacement has not been investigated.

In parallel, the above studies assume that the friction coefficient does not depend on pressure or velocity, which is clearly a simplification [23, 28]. It has not been studied whether pressure or velocity would alter the way that the vertical component influences the sliding response of rigid blocks.

This research attempts to comprehensively quantify the effect of the vertical component of seismic excitations on the response of sliding rigid blocks. Multi-stripe analysis (MSA) [34] is performed to assess the sliding response with and without the vertical component for a wide range of ground motion intensities. Contrary to previous work, not only maximum but residual sliding displacements as well are assessed and the values of the parameter space include relatively larger friction coefficients. Initially, to limit the parameters of the problem, a Coulomb friction model is employed to perform a parametric analysis. In this case, the selected friction model does not account for any dependence of the friction coefficient on velocity or pressure. Then, the model is refined to account for variations of the friction coefficient with velocity and pressure, something that has not been done before for sliding systems without restoring force. As this increases the parameters of the problem, two indicative sliding interface cases are examined: i) steel-steel, and ii) concrete-concrete surface.

2. Sliding response of rigid blocks under horizontal and vertical ground motions

Fig. 1 presents the typical case of an unanchored rigid block supported on a rigid base and subjected to horizontal and vertical excitations \ddot{u}_{gx} , \ddot{u}_{gy} , \ddot{u}_{gz} . It is assumed that the slenderness of the block (aspect ratio width/height) is high enough to prevent rocking. In this case, sliding is the main seismic response mechanism of the block and the equations of motion in the x and y directions are:

$$m \cdot \ddot{u}_x + F_x = -m \cdot \ddot{u}_{gx} \quad (1a)$$

$$m \cdot \ddot{u}_y + F_y = -m \cdot \ddot{u}_{gy} \quad (1b)$$

where m is the mass of the block, u_x and u_y are the sliding displacements, and F_x and F_y are the frictional forces.

It is assumed that the block is free to slide to infinitely large displacements. Hence it does not reach any sort of "failure".

Notably, even small and unintended inclinations of the sliding plane will result in gross underestimation of the sliding displacement, if a) the inclination is not explicitly taken into account [35], and b) the coefficient of friction is relatively small [36]. Therefore, the analysis

presented in this paper refers only to the idealized case of a perfectly horizontal case.

Moreover, as the friction coefficient tends to zero, the sliding displacement tends to the exact opposite of the ground displacement, which, in turn, is grossly affected by the correction methods (baseline and band pass filtering) that were applied to it [16]. Therefore, for very low coefficients of friction, the accuracy of the results predicted by Equation (1) is controlled by the accuracy that the ground displacement was recorded or deduced. A broader discussion on aleatory and epistemic uncertainty is offered in [37].

Previous studies developed a Stribeck friction model that can account for the different values of static and kinetic friction coefficients [26,27]. However, since the difference between static and average kinetic friction coefficients is relatively minor (e.g. 5% for a desk on common flooring materials [23]), the difference of static and kinetic friction is usually neglected when sliding components are studied.

Friction can be efficiently modelled using the Bouc-Wen model [38–41], which is used to represent generic bilinear hysteretic systems and has been suggested for sliding isolation bearings [42]:

$$F_x = \alpha \cdot K_{yield} \cdot u_x + (1 - \alpha) \cdot F_{yield} \cdot z_x \quad (2a)$$

$$F_y = \alpha \cdot K_{yield} \cdot u_y + (1 - \alpha) \cdot F_{yield} \cdot z_y \quad (2b)$$

where K_{yield} and F_{yield} are the pre-yield stiffness and force, α is the ratio of post-yield to pre-yield stiffness, which is set to 0 for sliding, and z_x and z_y are the dimensionless hysteretic parameters. To couple the biaxial hysteretic behavior, the formulation by Harvey and Gavin [43] is used and z_x and z_y [43] are set to:

$$\dot{z}_x = \frac{1}{u_{yield}} \left[A \dot{u}_x - z_x (\beta |\dot{u}_x z_x| + \gamma \dot{u}_x z_x + \beta |\dot{u}_y z_y| + \gamma \dot{u}_y z_y) (z_x^2 + z_y^2)^{\frac{\eta-2}{2}} \right] \quad (3a)$$

$$\dot{z}_y = \frac{1}{u_{yield}} \left[A \dot{u}_y - z_y (\beta |\dot{u}_x z_x| + \gamma \dot{u}_x z_x + \beta |\dot{u}_y z_y| + \gamma \dot{u}_y z_y) (z_x^2 + z_y^2)^{\frac{\eta-2}{2}} \right] \quad (3b)$$

where u_{yield} is the yield displacement, A , β , and γ control the shape of the hysteresis, and η governs the smoothness of the elastic-to-inelastic transition [43] (Fig. 2).

For the above model to simulate friction, (a) u_{yield} needs to be sufficiently small – in this study set to 0.1 mm according to [28] and (b) F_{yield} is set to:

$$F_{yield} = \mu \cdot m (\dot{u}_{gz} + g) \quad (4)$$

where g is the gravity acceleration and μ is the coefficient of friction, which may depend on sliding velocity, axial pressure, and temperature at the sliding surface. Later on, Section 4 assumes a constant coefficient of friction, while Section 5 assumes a dependence on sliding velocity and pressure.

Fig. 1. Unanchored rigid block under horizontal and vertical excitations.

Fig. 2. Bouc-Wen model: (a) Two-spring parallel system representation; (b) Model parameters.

Substituting Eqs. (2) into (1), gives:

$$\ddot{u}_x = -\mu \cdot (\ddot{u}_{gz} + g) \cdot z_x - \ddot{u}_{gx} \quad (5a)$$

$$\ddot{u}_y = -\mu \cdot (\ddot{u}_{gz} + g) \cdot z_y - \ddot{u}_{gy} \quad (5b)$$

In this study, the Bouc-Wen model is adopted, while MATLAB's ode45 solver [44] is used to numerically solve the state-space representation of differential equations for z_x and z_y . The relative and absolute error tolerances were set to 10^{-3} and 10^{-6} , respectively.

The values of A , β , and γ were set to 1, 0.5, and 0.5, according to [43]. To balance computation cost with accuracy, a value of $\eta = 4$ was chosen by performing a preliminary sensitivity analysis described in Section 4.

3. Multi-stripe analysis

To comprehensively quantify the effect of the vertical component of natural ground motions on the sliding response, MSA [34] is used as the computational tool for performing nonlinear dynamic analyses with and without the vertical component. Analysis is performed by using the natural ground motions that were selected by Kohrangi et al. [45] to be consistent with the seismic hazard at the site of Elefsina, Greece. Specifically, an approach based on the conditional spectrum [46] was employed, appropriately extended to allow achieving hazard consistency in both the horizontal and the vertical directions. The geometric mean of the spectral acceleration of the horizontal components for a vibration period of 0.3 s and 5 % viscous damping was employed as the conditioning IM. Per stripe of intensity measure (IM) the selected ground motions are scaled to match the IM values that correspond to a specific hazard level. Selection by Kohrangi et al. [45] considers 7 hazard levels with 77 natural ground motions per level; all are selected from the NGA-West2 database [47] to align with the horizontal and vertical conditional spectra, using the conditional-spectrum-based approach [45]. All selected ground motions were recorded on firm soil. More than 90 % of ground motions are ordinary records, while some records (less than 10 %) are characterized as pulse-like, mainly at high IM levels. In order to convert the IM from spectral acceleration to the peak ground acceleration, the procedure of Lachanas et al. [15] was followed. Specifically, to maintain the desirable hazard consistency of conditional-spectrum-based selected sets, the horizontal components of each record in each stripe were separately rescaled so that their geometric mean peak ground horizontal acceleration (PGA_{hgm}) matches the desired target value. Per stripe (IM level), the latter was set equal to the median PGA_{hgm} value of the 77 scaled records of the initial selection that was performed conditioned on the spectral acceleration. In all cases, the vertical components were scaled by the same factors as the corresponding horizontal ones. Hence, seven IM levels (stripes) conditioned on PGA_{hgm} were structured corresponding to IM values ranging from 0.15 g to 1.16 g. In order to examine higher IM levels, two extra stripes

were also considered by scaling the records of the stripe with $PGA_{hgm} = 1.16$ g to the values of 1.30 g and 1.50 g as shown in Fig. 3. Thus, in total 9 stripes of 77 ground motions per stripe are considered herein by taking PGA_{hgm} as the IM versus the maximum absolute (u_{max}) and the absolute residual (u_{res}) sliding displacements as engineering demand parameters (EDPs).

It is important here to note that during analysis, the vertical component affects the axial pressure applied to the block. If the vertical downward acceleration exceeds g , the unanchored block would lose contact with the surface and jump. To account for this, acceleration histories of records in the nine intensity levels were examined. Fig. 3 shows the percentage of records that cause the block to slide or jump for all the IM levels examined. It indicates that in all levels records with a scaled vertical component exceeding 1 g are less than 12 % and mainly consider the high IM levels. In low IM levels this percentage is lower than 5 %. To avoid including analysis cases with disputable physical consistency, these records were excluded from the analysis, assuming that (due to their small number) neglecting them would not induce significant bias in the results.

4. General study on sliding response with and without vertical component

This section neglects any velocity and pressure effect on the coefficient of friction and performs a broad parametric analysis to understand the effect of the vertical component on the maximum and residual displacement of the sliding block. The Euclidean norm of the displacement is used, i.e. $u = \sqrt{(u_x^2 + u_y^2)}$. The parametric analysis is performed for friction coefficient ranging between 0.05 and 0.8.

Fig. 3. Percentage of records with jumping and no jumping behavior per intensity level.

Throughout the analysis a value of u_{yield} (0.0001 m) was used to approximate rigid-perfectly-plastic behavior [28]. Regarding the value of η , Harvey and Gavin [48] adopted $\eta = 7$ to represent the behavior of actual structures. To choose the appropriate value of η , a preliminary sensitivity analysis was conducted on the sliding response of a block under horizontal and vertical earthquakes with $PGA_{hgm} = 0.61$ g and $\mu = 0.4$. The η values were 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7. Using $\eta = 7$ as a benchmark, the errors in maximum and residual displacements for $\eta = 2, 3, 4, 5$, and 6 are shown in Fig. 4. The errors increase as η decrease, while computational time decreases accordingly. Notably, errors of maximum and residual displacements remain below 2% and 5%, respectively, when $\eta = 4$. Thus, this study adopted $\eta = 4$ to balance computation cost with accuracy.

4.1. Comparison on a single ground motion basis

To assess the effect of the vertical component, the differences in maximum and residual displacements (Δu_{max}^{ij} and Δu_{res}^{ij}) are defined as:

$$\Delta u_{max}^{ij} = u_{max,v}^{ij} - u_{max,nv}^{ij} \quad (6)$$

$$\Delta u_{res}^{ij} = u_{res,v}^{ij} - u_{res,nv}^{ij} \quad (7)$$

where $u_{max,v}^{ij}$ and $u_{res,v}^{ij}$ are the maximum and residual displacements for the record j at stripe i when both vertical and horizontal components are considered, and $u_{max,nv}^{ij}$ and $u_{res,nv}^{ij}$ are the corresponding results when only considering the horizontal component. Fig. 5 presents the results for 77 records at stripe No. 4 ($PGA_{hgm} = 0.61$ g) with and without the vertical component when $\mu = 0.4$. It shows that accounting for the vertical component can increase both maximum and residual displacement up to 0.04 m (e.g. record No. 62), while there are few cases where the vertical component decreases displacements—but by no more than 0.02 m (e.g. No. 52). Interestingly, there are ground motions for which the vertical ground motion significantly increases the maximum displacement but only slightly increases the residual (e.g. No. 40), or vice versa (e.g. No. 75). In record case No. 31, the vertical component reduces the maximum displacement, while it increases the residual displacement. These observations are related to the characteristics of the ground motion waveform. From the results presented in Fig. 5 it is observed that on a single record basis, the influence of the vertical component shows significant variability regarding both maximum and residual sliding displacement. The higher seismic demand values that are mainly calculated when taking the vertical component into account range from negligible to non-negligible on a single record basis, whereas there are also few cases where it seems to have a “beneficial” effect on sliding response. Thus, since a solid answer on the influence of the vertical component on the sliding response is difficult to be given on a single record basis, a statistical approach should be adopted as it has been suggested and applied in previous studies [4,14–16,49,50–56] in order to search for answers on an ensemble-of-records basis.

4.2. Statistical comparison on a sample of ground motions basis

Since a comparison on a single record basis offers limited insight, this section compares some response statistics in each of the nine IM stripes (excluding the jumping cases). Boxplots of the difference between the responses with and without the vertical components are shown and discussed. Response ratios are also computed to quantify the effect of the vertical component. The ratios of the maximum and residual displacements (R_{max}^{ij} and R_{res}^{ij}) are defined as:

$$R_{max}^{ij} = \frac{u_{max,v}^{ij}}{u_{max,nv}^{ij}} \quad (8)$$

$$R_{res}^{ij} = \frac{u_{res,v}^{ij}}{u_{res,nv}^{ij}} \quad (9)$$

Note that when the μ/PGA_{hgm} is sufficiently high, Coulomb friction assumes no displacement, as there is no sliding. In this case, the threshold value is not necessarily equal to 1, because of the vertical component of the excitation and because the geomean value of the peak ground acceleration (PGA_{hgm}) is employed as IM instead of the maximum of the Euclidian norm of the horizontal peak ground acceleration. However, the Bouc-Wen model does compute a very low value of displacement (lower than $u_y = 0.1$ mm). To avoid any numerical issues (i.e. the ratios of Eqs. (8) and (9) being meaningless), a value of $1e-9$ m was assigned to any maximum or residual displacement being smaller than 0.001 m. These cases are considered as “no sliding” cases.

Fig. 6 shows the percentage of the “sliding” cases for the different μ and PGA_{hgm} values. Solid bars offer values when the vertical component is considered, while hollow bars when the vertical component is neglected. As expected, as the value of the Coulomb friction coefficient (μ) increases, the block requires higher IM levels to initiate sliding. When μ is set to 0.05 and 0.1, sliding behavior is observed across all IM levels, irrespectively of whether the vertical component is considered. However, for values of μ/PGA_{hgm} between 1.11 and 1.33 the vertical component significantly influences the initiation of sliding, as the hollow and solid bars significantly differ. In these cases, including the vertical component “accelerates” the initiation of sliding, and thus, if the performance objective is to avoid sliding, the vertical component should be included into analysis.

4.2.1. Maximum displacement

Figs. 7 and 8 show the boxplots of the difference (Δu_{max}^{ij}) and of the ratio (R_{max}^{ij}) of maximum displacement when μ ranges from 0.05 to 0.8. In each vertical stripe, i.e. IM level, the central cross mark denotes the median value; the notches indicate the 95% confidence interval of the median; the top and bottom edges of the box represent the 25th percentile and 75th percentile values; while the upper whisker is the smallest of 1.5 times the interquartile range (IQR) plus the 75th percentile and the maximum value, and the lower whisker is the largest of 1.5 times IQR minus the 25th percentile value and the minimum

Fig. 4. Effect of η on sliding response for the PGA_{hgm} level of 0.61 g and μ of 0.4.

Fig. 5. Effect of vertical component on sliding response for the PGA_{hgm} level of 0.61 g: (a) Maximum displacement; (b) Residual displacement.

Fig. 6. Percentage of ground motions per IM level with sliding behavior (i.e., sliding is initiated) with and without the vertical component for different cases of Coulomb coefficient of friction.

value. The solid rhombuses represent the data points falling outside the whiskers and are considered outliers. The top and bottom asterisk markers represent the maximum and minimum values of each dataset.

For relatively low values of μ (smaller than 0.1) the vertical component does not seem to influence the maximum displacement as the error seems to be less than 15 % (in terms of 25 and 75 percentile of the ratio R_{max} — Fig. 8). This can be explained physically by considering that at the limit case where $\mu = 0$, the frictional force is always zero and the maximum displacement is equal to the Peak Ground Displacement, irrespectively of whether the vertical acceleration is included. So, as μ tends to zero, it is expected that Δu_{max} also tends to zero and R_{max} tends to 1. When μ becomes larger than 0.1 (Figs. 7 and 8(c-i)) the vertical component does influence the median maximum displacement. For large enough values of μ the difference again becomes zero, as friction becomes too large and does not allow for the block to slide with or without the vertical component. Still this cannot be observed in the plots provided in Figs. 7 and 8 for the IM levels with $PGA_{hgm} = 1.16$ g, 1.30 g and 1.50 g (or in the work of Lopez Garcia and Soong [21] and Arshad and Konstantinidis [28]) because μ was not set to large enough values to clamp the block for such high PGAs. The weird form of some boxplots (e. g. Fig. 8h, $PGA_{hgm} = 0.61$ g) means that the 25 percentile is larger than the lower bound of the confidence interval of the median value.

More insight is gained by Fig. 9. Fig. 9a offers the median displacement difference, Δu_{max} , as a function of μ . Note that to construct curves with an adequate density of data points, further analyses were performed for cases with μ below 0.05 [57] and exceeding 0.8 [58], alongside an increased resolution for intermediate values of μ . It indicates that stronger ground motions (i.e. motions with larger PGA_{hgm}) cause larger difference between the maximum displacement of the

“vertical component included” and “no vertical component included” cases. This is expected, as stronger ground motions would cause larger maximum displacements overall. Fig. 9b plots the median displacement ratio, R_{max} , as a function of μ . It shows that, in terms of ratio R_{max} the influence of the vertical component is small for small μ cases. As μ increases the influence initially becomes larger and after it attains a peak, it diminishes for large enough μ . Fig. 9c plots the median displacement ratio as a function of $\mu g / PGA_{hgm}$, i.e. normalized strength as referred to by Makris and Black [59]. It shows that by normalizing μg with PGA_{hgm} the ratio R_{max} attains a maximum value for $\mu g / PGA_{hgm}$ in the neighborhood of 1, showing that the influence of the vertical component is most important when the ground motion can barely induce sliding. Moreover, one can observe that this maximum value is larger for larger PGA_{hgm} values. On the same plot, one can observe that there is a second local maximum of the curve for values of $\mu g / PGA_{hgm}$ around 0.2. However, the value of this local maximum is rather low (increase less than 10 %).

Fig. 10 illustrates the maximum displacement normalized over μ for the analysis (a) without and (b) with the vertical component versus the normalized strength ($\mu g / PGA_{hgm}$). Interestingly, this normalization leads to the collapse of all the different PGA_{hgm} curves to two single master curves (one with and one without vertical excitation) without having an obvious physical meaning. These curves confirm that for small values of $\mu g / PGA_{hgm}$ the vertical component of the excitation does not influence the maximum response. Indicatively, for $\mu g / PGA_{hgm} = 0.25$ the normalized displacement for both cases is 0.43. As $\mu g / PGA_{hgm}$ approaches 1, differences start to arise: for $\mu g / PGA_{hgm}$ within the range of 0.25 to 0.75, the normalized displacement with the vertical component of the excitation ($u_{max,v} / \mu$) does not increase by more than 0.03 compared to

Fig. 7. Boxplots of the difference of maximum displacement with and without vertical component as computed via Eq. (6) for the MSA results of different μ cases.

the values without the vertical component $(u_{max,nv})_{50\%}/\mu$.

4.2.2. Residual displacement

Figs. 11 and 12 present the boxplots of the difference (Δu_{res}) and ratio (R_{res}) of residual displacements with and without the vertical component. Similar to the results for the maximum displacement and for the same physical reasons, for $\mu < 0.1$ the vertical component does not seem to influence the residual displacement (at least for the PGA_{hgm} levels considered). As the value of μ increases, the effect of the vertical component becomes more pronounced, and it can increase the median residual displacement up to 100%. In this case, the influence of the vertical component on the seismic demand seems to be higher than that on the maximum displacement. As shown, with the only exception of the low μ cases, the median ratio is over 1 in almost all IM levels.

Figs. 13a and 13b plot the median values of the difference (Δu_{res}) and ratio (R_{res}) of the residual displacement against the friction coefficient for all PGA_{hgm} levels. As with maximum displacement, stronger ground motions cause larger residual displacements. For a given PGA_{hgm} level, when μ approaches zero (low friction cases of smooth surfaces) practically there is no influence of the vertical component of the ground motion on the residual sliding response as it can be observed from the median $(\Delta u_{res})_{50\%}$ values in Fig. 13a. As μ increases the median difference, $(\Delta u_{res})_{50\%}$, follows a non-monotonic pattern: It increases to an overall maximum, then decreases and increases again to a local maximum and then tends to zero. The form of the residual displacement ratio $(R_{res})_{50\%}$ is simpler as all curves start from 1, increase to a global maximum and then decrease to 1. If $(R_{res})_{50\%}$ is plotted against the normalized strength $\mu g/PGA_{hgm}$ of the system, it can be observed that the

Fig. 8. Boxplots of ratio of maximum displacement with vertical component over without as computed via Eq. (8) for the MSA results of different μ cases.

global maximum of $(R_{res})_{50\%}$ occurs for $\mu g/PGA_{hgm}$ around 1. Moreover, it can be observed that for smaller values of $\mu g/PGA_{hgm}$, the relative displacement ratio $(R_{res})_{50\%}$ of the residual displacements seems to attain higher values than its maximum displacement counterpart $(R_{max})_{50\%}$.

Finally, Fig. 14 shows that normalizing the residual displacements with μ makes all the curves of different PGA_{hgm} collapse to two master curves: One when vertical excitation is not included (Fig. 14a) and one when it is included (Fig. 14b). For $\mu g/PGA_{hgm} < 0.2$ the two master curves attain similar values, while for larger $\mu g/PGA_{hgm}$ ranging from 0.25 to 0.75, including the vertical component can increase the normalized residual displacement up to 0.07.

5. Case study on sliding response with and without vertical component

In all the results presented in the previous section it was assumed that the coefficient of friction is independent of the pressure and the sliding velocity. This simplified approach is a necessary assumption in order to reduce the parameters of the problem and allow for a detailed parametric analysis. In this section, a more refined model is employed regarding the friction, which takes into account the dependence of friction coefficient on the pressure (i.e., the pressure of the vertical load that the object transmits to the interface) and the sliding velocity [60, 61]. To keep the parameters of the problem to a reasonably small number, two case-studies will be presented for specific interface materials.

Fig. 9. Relationship between friction coefficient and effect of vertical component on maximum displacement.

Fig. 10. Relationships between normalized acceleration of ground motion and maximum displacement (a) No vertical; (b) With vertical.

5.1. Case 1: steel on steel interface

Tamai et al. [60] developed a nonlinear friction coefficient model for steel-steel interfaces that considers the effects of sliding velocity and axial pressure and is described by:

$$\mu = -0.003144 \cdot \ln(v) - 0.007024 \cdot \ln(p/\sigma \cdot 10^3) + 0.2016 \quad (10)$$

where v is the sliding velocity in mm/s, p is the applied pressure on the steel-steel interface in MPa, and σ is the yield strength of the steel (is set equal to 177 MPa [60]). Figs. 15a to 15c plot the friction coefficient

Fig. 11. Boxplots of the difference of residual displacement with and without vertical component.

against the sliding velocity under three levels of axial pressure (namely $p = 10$ MPa, 20 MPa, and 40 MPa). The constant coefficient of friction model was defined by setting a velocity of 0.2 m/s and a pressure of 10 MPa in Eq. (10) to yield a coefficient of friction $\mu = 0.1556$. The variable coefficient of friction model used Eq. (10) which was directly implemented to Matlab.

Figs. 16a and 16b show the percentage of the sliding, no sliding, and jumping cases of a steel-steel interface using a constant coefficient of friction with and without the vertical component. Most of PGA_{hgm} levels are significantly larger than the friction coefficient. The only level where including the vertical component or using a variable friction model influenced the initiation of sliding was that of $PGA_{hgm} = 0.15$ g. But even there, the influence seems to be marginal as the percentage of sliding cases is slightly changed for the cases where the vertical component of

ground motion is taken into account; regardless of employing a constant or a variable coefficient of friction.

Figs. 17 and 18 present the median values and standard deviation of R_{max} and R_{res} calculated per IM level for a steel-steel interface. Note that for the $PGA_{hgm} = 0.15$ g bin, the standard deviation reaches extremely large values. This is because for this bin there were cases where not including the vertical component resulted in no sliding, while including it resulted in sliding. Therefore, the ratios R_{max} and R_{res} for these cases reach extremely high values, and this reflects into the standard deviation of these quantities. In most cases a variable μ model yields practically the same results with a constant μ model, with the only exception being the standard deviation of the residual displacement for large PGA_{hgm} values. In this case, using a variable friction model seems to decrease the dispersion of the results.

Fig. 12. Boxplots of ratio of residual displacement with vertical component over without.

5.2. Case 2: concrete on concrete interface

Fronteddu et al. [61] performed several sliding friction tests on concrete blocks of different manufacturing and treatment methods. This

section focuses on the blocks that were not treated and were produced by failing a beam in bending. The model that was proposed takes into account the influence of the pressure (but not of the velocity) on the friction coefficient and is given by:

$$\mu = \begin{cases} \frac{0.85 \cdot (0.95 - 0.00022 \cdot p) + 0.15 \cdot (0.3 - 0.00005 \cdot p)}{1 - 0.85 \cdot 0.15 \cdot (0.95 - 0.00022 \cdot p)(0.3 - 0.00005 \cdot p)} & \text{for } p \leq 500\text{kPa} \\ \frac{0.85 \cdot (0.865 - 0.00005 \cdot p) + 0.15 \cdot (0.3 - 0.00005 \cdot p)}{1 - 0.85 \cdot 0.15 \cdot (0.865 - 0.00005 \cdot p)(0.3 - 0.00005 \cdot p)} & \text{for } 500\text{kPa} < p \leq 2000\text{kPa} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Fig. 13. Relationship between friction coefficient and effect of vertical component on residual displacement.

Fig. 14. Relationships between normalized acceleration of ground motion and residual displacement (a) No vertical; (b) With vertical.

where p is the applied pressure on the concrete-concrete interface in kPa. Fig. 19 plots Eq. (11).

This section will study three different levels of pressure $p = 10$ kPa, 500 kPa, 1000 kPa using a constant and a variable friction model. Note

the $p = 500$ kPa model corresponds to the point where the slope of the μ - p curve changes (Fig. 19). For the constant friction model, $p = 10$ kPa or $p = 500$ kPa or $p = 1000$ kPa is set to Eq. (11) to obtain a constant $\mu = 0.8825$, $\mu = 0.7782$, and $\mu = 0.7497$, respectively. For the variable friction model, the coefficient of friction changes according to Eq. (11)

Fig. 15. Variation in friction coefficient on a steel-steel interface.

Fig. 16. Matching behavior in Case 1 (steel on steel): (a) Excluding vertical component using a constant coefficient of friction; (b) Including vertical component using a constant coefficient; (c) Including vertical component using a variable friction coefficient.

(which was directly implemented to Matlab), because the pressure changes due to the vertical acceleration.

Fig. 20a shows the sliding / no sliding / jumping cases of the model using a constant coefficient of friction ($p = 500$ kPa) without the inclusion of the vertical component. Fig. 20b uses a constant coefficient of friction and includes the vertical component and Fig. 20c uses a variable coefficient of friction and includes the vertical motion. Overall the differences are negligible with the exception of the 0.61 g bin (again close to $\mu g / PGA_{hgm} = 1$), where including the vertical component facilitates sliding.

Fig. 21 presents the median values of R_{max} and R_{res} for a variable and a constant coefficient of friction. For the $p = 100$ kPa and $p = 1000$ kPa

pressures, using the variable coefficient of friction model does not have any influence of the effect of the vertical component on the maximum and residual displacements. The only case where using the more refined model seems to matter is for the $p = 500$ kPa case (i.e. where the μ - p diagram changes slope).

Figs. 22a and 22b plot the normalized maximum and residual displacement ($(u_{max})_{50\%} / \mu$ and $(u_{res})_{50\%} / \mu$) versus the normalized strength $\mu g / PGA_{hgm}$, for $p = 500$ kPa. Three cases are considered: a) Without vertical component and with constant coefficient of friction; b) With vertical component and constant coefficient of friction; and c) With vertical component and variable coefficient of friction. The vertical component increases both the maximum and the residual displacement.

Fig. 17. Ratio of maximum displacement with vertical component over without in Case 1 (steel on steel): (a) Median value and (b) Standard deviation.

Fig. 18. Ratio of residual displacement with vertical component over without in Case 1 (steel on steel): (a) Median value and (b) Standard deviation.

Fig. 19. Variation in friction coefficient of a concrete block on a concrete surface.

In terms of absolute values, this increase is small, almost negligible. However, the careful reader will observe that when $\mu g/PGA_{hgm}$ lies in the neighborhood of 1, the percentage wise increase can be large. Finally, it seems that including the vertical component is more important than using a variable coefficient of friction.

6. Conclusions

This study investigated the effect of the vertical component of ground motions on the sliding response of rigid blocks, in terms of both maximum and residual displacements. It was assumed that the sliding surface is perfectly horizontal and that the excitation was corrected in a reliable way.

First, a comprehensive study was conducted using a constant coefficient of friction Coulomb model, considering a wide range of friction coefficient values. It can be concluded that:

- (1) On a single-ground-motion basis, the vertical component can increase or decrease the maximum and residual displacements.
- (2) On an ensemble-of-records basis, the vertical ground motion seems to have a non-negligible effect only when $\mu g/PGA_{hgm}$ is close to 1.00, where it increases both the maximum and residual displacement. It is worth noting that for $0.05 < \mu < 1.2$ and for $PGA_{hgm} < 1.5$ g, the median value of the difference in maximum displacement with and without the vertical component never exceeds 2 cm, while for the residuals it never exceeds 4 cm. However, the median values of the ratios between the maximum (or of the residual) displacement with and without the vertical component can reach values up to 2.5. Therefore, the relative error induced by not including the vertical component can be large, especially when $\mu g/PGA_{hgm}$ is close to 1.00.

Fig. 20. Matching behavior in Case 2: (a) Excluding vertical component using a constant coefficient of friction; (b) Including vertical component using a constant coefficient; (c) Including vertical component using a variable friction coefficient.

Fig. 21. Ratio of sliding displacement with vertical component over without in Case 2.

Fig. 22. Relationship between normalized acceleration of ground motion and sliding response: (a) Maximum displacement; (b) Residual displacement.

- (3) When $(u_{max})_{50\%}/\mu$ or $(u_{res})_{50\%}/\mu$ is plotted against $\mu g / PGA_{hgm}$ for different PGA_{hgm} bins, all plots fall on a master curve.

Next, two cases were analyzed to explore the effect of the vertical component on sliding response when the friction coefficient dependence is considered. The primary findings can be summarized as follows:

- (1) In the cases of the steel-steel interface, using a variable coefficient of friction appears to have negligible influence on maximum and residual displacements. The vertical component of ground motions has a minor effect on maximum displacement, while its effect on residual displacement is slightly more pronounced.
- (2) In the case of the concrete-concrete interface, using a variable coefficient of friction model overall does not influence the results, unless the pressure at the sliding interface is 500 kPa. This is attributed the special form of the μ - p relation that was used, as it is a bilinear curve that changes slope at 500 kPa.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Michalis Vassiliou: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Dimitrios Vamvatsikos:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Ying Zhou:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Zengde Zhang:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Christos G. Lachanas:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Resources, Methodology, Formal analysis.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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